

Article

Does Volunteering in a Language Learning Centre Help Non-Native English Speaking Students' Emotional Well-Being?

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Abstract

Feeling connected as one navigates life as a post-secondary student is a challenge for many students, both domestic and international. Many non-native speakers of English may not feel a sense of belonging or social connectedness at university and have emotional and other needs hindering their adjustment and success at university. Institutions often have various opportunities for students to volunteer at events, support centres, and other university units. Self-access centres, such as language learning centres and writing centres, have become common at many institutions and often have many student volunteers, making these an ideal environment for research on students. This study took place in one of these centres at a university in Canada - a language learning centre. In this study, researchers used a mixed methods approach to explore student volunteer perceptions. Survey responses that related to the emotional well-being of student volunteers were highlighted for this study. The data from the survey were then cross-referenced with the transcripts of the focus group study for further confirmation. Findings indicate that the act of volunteering in the centre made an impact on student volunteers' emotional well-being. It gave students a sense of belonging and the feeling that they were part of a greater community. It also helped reduce loneliness and build self-esteem.

Keywords

Student motivation, learning centre, volunteering, student emotional well-being

1 Introduction

University study can be challenging for all students given the various stress and pressures they face, and many relocate away from their families and home community. For international students, navigating life and study in a new linguistic, cultural, and academic context is often a daunting undertaking, perhaps even more so than for domestic students. It is known that non-native English speakers (NNES)

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studying internationally, for example, often do not feel socially connected and lack a sense of belonging (Hanassab, 2006). Compared to their domestic counterparts, international students have more stress, isolation, anxiety, homesickness, and a lack of confidence (Andrade, 2006). Educators who work closely with international students are likely not surprised by this as they observe the challenges many of their students face daily. Socio-cultural adjustment and other critical aspects of adapting to life in a new country are genuine challenges that many students face. To help students transition and be successful, universities offer varying support such as orientations, events, and student support initiatives. Furthermore, universities have various ways for students to become involved on campus such as through student clubs and volunteer opportunities. In terms of volunteering, self-access centres such as language learning centres and writing centres are found at many institutions and are common spaces in which students serve as volunteers. Beyond the motivations to volunteer which include developing new skills and gaining career-related experience, many students volunteer for social reasons and friendship (Holdsworth, 2010). This social element is important as students need to make new connections and feel a sense of belonging, something very important for students navigating a new academic, cultural, and linguistic life.

The study reported in this article focuses on a recently established Language Learning Centre (LLC) for English for Academic Purposes (EAP) students at a university in Canada. This self-access centre, which opened in fall 2017, is coordinated by a faculty member with the support of 2-3 teaching assistants and a team of volunteers. In response to student demand for support, the centre expanded to include volunteers to help a few months after opening. This not only provided more capacity for the centre to support students – of which, excluding special events, there were approximately 750 student visits in most semesters prior to the COVID-19 pandemic – but also opportunities for student volunteers to gain meaningful experience. In addition to providing tutorial support for EAP students, these volunteers help in other ways such as supporting the English Conversation Club, special events and workshops, and social activities. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic and the shift to remote online learning, approximately 15 volunteers worked in the centre in a typical semester. Notably, the majority of the volunteers are NNES international students or recent immigrants, and a number had also previously taken EAP classes in the university. Over time, it was observed that many of the volunteers, even when they were not scheduled to volunteer, spent a lot of time in the centre socializing with friends and students as well as helping with various activities at the centre.

By nature, self-access student support centres are just that - student-driven. Students have the autonomy to choose to access support or not. Additionally, many centres also provide flexible spaces for self-directed study or to relax and meet peers. The LLC focused on in this study is similar to many such centres. Tutors are available for student support on a drop-in basis. Additionally, the centre offers workshops, events, the English Conversation Club, and other social and support opportunities. Students can also use the space to study, access various resources, or relax. The LLC is located in a large and welcoming room that is flexibly designed and includes several areas such as sofas, movable desks, bean bag chairs, and a counter with computers and a printer for student use. Coffee and tea are available for students and refreshments are offered at some events. The centre is centrally located on campus in close proximity to where most EAP classes are held. Some important considerations for centres include stewardship, relevance, and interactivity (Sadler, 2011), with the operations of the LLC aligning with these ideas. For example, a guiding philosophy of the LLC has been to value all voices and to provide the opportunity for all team members to help guide the centre's operations and initiatives. Hence, this inclusive approach has valued ideas on initiatives and activities for the centre from the volunteers.

The participants in this study, predominantly non-native speakers of English (international students or new immigrants), have various motivations to volunteer and support EAP students in the LLC. They also have their own needs in transitioning to life and study in a new academic, linguistic, and cultural context. Notably, the majority of the volunteers in this study (90%) were students enrolled in graduate

programs in education. As newcomers to life and study in Canada, they have varied needs, including their own emotional and physical well-being. Moving to study in a new country takes significant courage and requires students to form new connections, particularly social ones. Moreover, international graduate students have additional challenges in adjusting to their studies compared to domestic or undergraduate students (Sullivan & Kashubeck-West, 2015). Curiosity on how volunteer opportunities help the emotional well-being of students arose from discussions and observations of student volunteers. The study described in this article seeks to explore if and how volunteering at this self-access language learning centre helps student well-being. The study addresses the following research question: Does volunteering in the language learning centre at a university help promote the emotional well-being of student volunteers?

2 Literature Review

University study is challenging for many, and all the more so for international students or newer immigrants. They face a unique set of challenges, particularly if they are non-native English speakers (NNES). This is notable as student demographics at Canadian universities have changed dramatically in recent years, with a significant increase in the number of international students (Anderson, 2015). In fact, 318,153 international students were enrolled in post-secondary contexts in Canada in 2019 (Statistics Canada, 2020). The challenges these NNES students face stem from a number of factors: language difficulties, lack of social contact, language barriers, little to no family support, financial stress, and new academic systems (Andrade, 2006; Chen et al, 2015; Mori, 2000; Zhang & Goodson, 2011). International students cope with change in various ways, including through social networking services (Lim & Meier, 2012). Andrade (2006) conducted a meta-analysis of studies on international students studying in English-speaking countries and found, perhaps not surprisingly, that international students had a higher level of isolation, anxiety, stress, homesickness, and a lack of confidence when compared to their domestic counterparts. Further, research has shown that international students tend to have greater mental health issues than domestic students, often reporting a higher level of stress (Forbes-Mewett & Sawyer, 2016). Simply the act of studying in a foreign country can increase a student's mental health concerns (Prieto-Welch, 2016). To that end, Girmay's (2019) study on the acculturation and the mental and physical health needs of international graduate students in the United States found that stereotypes and xenophobia also have an impact on students' mental health. Since mental health does not discriminate, it can affect individuals regardless of their background. Depression among international students is real and, in some cases, ends in tragedy (Smith, 2020). Indeed, studies have shown that emotional distress can lead to suicide ideation among international students (Taliaferro et al., 2020). These studies highlight the difficult reality that many international students face when they move to study in another country.

The pressures from family, friends, and sponsors back in the home country are among some of the greatest stress inducers students face while abroad (Misra & Castillo, 2004). For this reason and others, international students often face mental health disorders such as depression (Constantine et al., 2004; Rosenthal et al., 2008) which is a significant reason for international student visits to a university counsellor (Wei et al., 2008). This, however, should not come as a complete surprise to educators. Depression and anxiety are well-known psychological responses to living in foreign environments (Mesidor & Sly, 2016). Interestingly, research has shown that international students with lower proficiency in English, in particular, tend to suffer from depression (Constantine et al., 2004). In addition to lower English proficiency, loneliness is also known to trigger mental health issues. Sawir et al. (2008) surveyed 200 international students studying in Australia and found 130 of them suffered from social isolation or loneliness, particularly in the early months after their arrival. This research highlights how critical it is for universities to support international students in their first semester of study. The lack of belonging and sense of isolation is an issue for many international students, with Hanassab (2006)

finding this was highest for students from Africa, the Middle East, and Asia who were studying in the United States. A study of international students studying in smaller communities in Canada revealed that participants were less connected with the local community and tended to form multicultural friendships with other international students (Poteet & Gomez, 2015). Other studies have indicated the importance of making connections with the host country's national students throughout university life. In Australia, for example, a report on the wellbeing of international students noted that many find a sense of loneliness and isolation, in part due to limited interactions with local students (Ryan et al., 2016). Friendships between international students and host nationals have been found to be one of the more important channels that contribute towards both social satisfaction and social support (Hendrickson et al., 2011). Based on this, it appears that campus events and initiatives promoting the integration of international and domestic students benefit students.

Although the *overall* well-being of students needs to take centre stage throughout their studies, students' *emotional* well-being is of the utmost importance. Research has shown that a person's emotional well-being is closely linked to their physical well-being (Barry et al., 2019). For example, scientists found that high levels of stress can lead to viral infections (Cohen et al., 1991) and that the inability to control life events in general can lead to cardiovascular illness (Marmot et al., 1991). In fact, studies of the link between emotional well-being and physical well-being are quite extensive (e.g., Girmay, 2019; Johnson, 1990; Lee et al., 2017). This highlights the importance of supporting students' emotional well-being as they transition to being post-secondary students in another country.

Emotional well-being definitions abound in the literature. The U.S. Department of Health and Human Services (2021) defines emotional well-being as "the ability to successfully handle life's stresses and adapt to change and difficult times" (para 1). This translates into experiencing fewer negative emotions and having greater emotional resilience. Others describe it more as a general positive state of being, denoting a good emotional connection with other people and one's environment and personal satisfaction with one's life (Ostir et al., 2000). Yet others link emotional intelligence, which is a person's ability to recognise and regulate one's emotions, closely to one's emotional well-being, with the latter being more about strong self-esteem and positive feelings (Schutte et al., 2010). For this study, the general definition of feeling positive emotions and increased self-esteem will be used to describe emotional well-being.

Social connections are important for students. Sümer et al. (2011) found that social support (or the lack thereof) was a predictor of anxiety and depression in international students. One way to help international students with their emotional well-being is to assist them as quickly as possible with adjusting to university life and their studies thereafter. This includes creating a sense of belonging for them and making them feel part of a greater community. Girmay (2019) offered other suggestions to help address international student support needs, including pairing international students with a domestic student, identifying supports and aid available, and de-stigmatizing mental health support. These and other approaches can help students in varied ways.

Volunteering is well-known to increase the psychological well-being of those in the general population of society, especially for those who volunteer for longer periods of time and who have lower levels of happiness (Binder & Freytag, 2013; Jiang et al., 2021; Piliavin & Siegl, 2007). Tran (2020) argued people-to-people connections and empathy are important, and that in order "to position international students as truly an integral component of campus communities, it is essential to develop explicit approaches to engage them not only academically and interculturally, but also mentally and emotionally" (p. xiii). This consideration is important, and the act of volunteering, particularly in an academic setting on campus may offer means for students to engage and connect mentally and emotionally. Studies on university student volunteers and emotional well-being show similar results to that of the general population. Shadowen et al.'s (2019) study on international students studying in the United States found that depressive symptoms were lower when there was increased social support. An European study on university students in Italy and Ukraine found both cohorts' emotional well-

being improved with the act of volunteering (Balashov et al., 2018). Notably, a U.S. study that covered 129 institutions across the country found university students who volunteered 1-9 hours per week experienced fewer depressive symptoms (Lederer et al., 2015). This is echoed by another recent study conducted on university students in the U.S. where findings indicated volunteering can lower anxiety and depression in students (Cliff, 2020). It would stand to reason, then, that international students would also benefit emotionally from volunteering on campus. The literature to date does not appear to address the topic in terms of *international students'* volunteering on campus and the resulting emotional benefits. One study on international students studying English in Canada; however, did look at challenges that students studying in Canada face. That study offered suggestions for how students can navigate culture shock, mental health challenges, and identity loss (Carter, 2016). Carter recommended ways in which international students may help carve out their identity and adapt through extra-curricular activities including volunteering and living in homestays. To investigate the notion that volunteering at the Language Learning Centre helps students' emotional well-being, further investigation was needed. This resulted in the following research question: Does volunteering in the Language Learning Centre at a university help promote the emotional well-being of student volunteers?

3 Methods

In this study, data was drawn from an existing mixed-method study that explored student motivations and perceptions of the Language Learning Centre in which students volunteered. A study consisting of a survey and interviews with focus groups was chosen for the original research for a number of reasons. Firstly, a more in-depth examination of the research question often results from a mixed methods approach as it allows for the collection and analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data (Creswell & Clark, 2017). According to Dörnyei (2007), this is a form of triangulation where data sources are combined “to study the same phenomenon” (p. 43) which allows for the strengths of different methods to make up for any deficiencies the other methods in the study may have. It is important to note that many researchers have used mixed methods in applied linguistics – with Magnan (2006) citing 6.8% of all studies in *The Modern Language Journal* making use of this approach in a ten-year period alone. The structure of the focus groups, in particular, was important as it allowed for the participants to expand on their perceptions beyond the initial questions and resulted in comments that touched on a number of aspects of their experience as volunteers.

This study used existing data from a mixed-method study on student volunteer motivations at a university Language Learning Centre in Canada. The researchers highlighted survey questions (see Appendix A) that related to the emotional well-being of student volunteers. Each question was then cross-referenced with the interview transcripts (from audio recordings) of the focus group study (around twenty minutes each in duration) for further confirmation of the phenomenon in question (see Appendix B for interview questions). For example, the entire set of transcripts from the focus group study was analyzed to find evidence supporting the results of the survey question “I feel less lonely due to volunteering.” Any comments in the focus group transcripts that supported the survey result were highlighted and cross-referenced with the survey data. Research ethics approval was received prior to data collection.

3.1 Participants

All student volunteers, including those who provided support at the LLC in the past were invited to partake in the online survey. Of the 50 volunteers, 30 students, of whom 28 identified as non-native English speakers, participated in the survey, with 27 of the 30 respondents (90%) identifying as graduate

students. Of these participants, a convenience sample of eight volunteers, seven of whom were NNES students, was used in the focus group study, forming three groups. One participant in this focus group study had worked both as a volunteer and teaching assistant. Group one had two participants, and groups two and three each had three participants. The participants ranged from undergraduate to graduate to recently-convocated, with the greatest representation being that of students studying in the university's Master of Education program. The interviews in the focus group study were audio-recorded and transcribed for analysis.

4 Findings

The study findings revealed that several aspects of emotional well-being were being fostered by volunteering at the language learning centre. Table 1 shows responses to the statements on volunteer motivations, perceptions, and experiences relating to emotional well-being.

Table 1

Survey Responses to Statements Relating to Student Volunteer Motivations, Perceptions and Experiences

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Volunteering is an opportunity to be part of a teaching and learning community	0	0	11(36.67%)	19 (63.33%)
I feel more connected to peers and others through volunteering	1 (3.33%)	2 (6.67%)	9 (30%)	18 (60%)
I feel less lonely due to volunteering	0	2 (6.67%)	13 (43.33%)	15 (50%)
Through volunteering, my self-esteem has increased	0	2 (6.67%)	12 (40%)	16 (53.33%)
Volunteering makes me feel important	0	4 (13.33%)	12 (40%)	14 (46.67%)
My friends volunteer and I want to work with them	3 (10%)	4 (13.33%)	11 (36.67%)	12 (40%)
Volunteering helps me forget about some of my personal problems	4 (13.33%)	9 (30%)	9 (30%)	8 (26.67%)
I can learn how to work with a variety of people through volunteering	0	2 (6.67%)	10 (33.33%)	18 (60%)
Volunteering is an opportunity to make new friends	1 (3.33%)	0	11 (36.67%)	18 (60%)

Responses to the survey questions in Table 1 highlight how the experience of volunteering impacted students positively, particularly in terms of their social relationships. Firstly, a sense of belonging and being part of something greater emerged, with 100% of student volunteers agreeing that volunteering at the centre helped them be part of a teaching and learning community. The results also indicated how the experience was positive in regard to mitigating the students' sense of loneliness and building their self-esteem, with 93.33% of students indicating that volunteering made them feel less lonely and 90% indicating they felt more connected to peers and others through volunteering in the centre.

The focus group study confirmed these survey results. The following data emerged in response to a question about what the volunteer students particularly enjoyed.

A: Uh... the first thing is *communicating with other students from different major*.

B: ... also I enjoyed because I feel like *my peers...uh... are my friends and also kind of like my family...*

In response to a question about reasons for volunteering in the centre, students noted the following:

C: *I also wanted some teaching experience ... ah... so... umm... I wanted to contribute...umm... more or less... umm...ah... learn more about what the campus can offer ...umm... to M.Ed. students like me. I think [volunteering in the LLC] gives us ...umm...umm... a better working experience ... umm... looking at umm... who are on campus, you know meeting people... umm... one and ... umm... building connections.*

D: ...so for me maybe in the future, I'm not sure if I have an opportunity to stay in [the city] or stay at [the university], maybe I can get some opportunity to get position, right? So, for ... *I want to make myself famous.*

E: I would say for personal... umm... *you know you really get a sense of community... like in the LLC because ... for me... I have a lot of friends there and sometimes there is a bunch of us Tas and volunteers just there talking about like what is education all about and like what we can do to help all the people... you know... just so many things in general... like...umm... sort of like a networking...*

The italicized parts of the above responses indicate that student volunteers felt they were part of a greater community on campus through their volunteer work. They felt they were making both professional and peer connections, and – perhaps – even building a reputation in the learning and teaching community on campus in order to secure employment there. The survey responses to a closely related question showed that 90% (27 out of 30) of the student volunteers felt a greater social connection with peers and others as a result of volunteering at the centre with 93% (28 out of 30) of the respondents reporting feeling less lonely. In fact, 97% (29 out of 30) recognized that volunteering at the centre was an opportunity to make new friends.

A: [I particularly enjoyed] the games section. Like we are playing board games together and then yeah. *We communicate, we are laughing, we're just enjoy the games, yeah.*

B: ... also I enjoyed because I feel like *my peers...uh... are my friends and also kind of like my family...*

D: ...for my experiences in the LLC, I you know, I uh you know... *I contact to with any all the other students right and I feel of that the atmosphere was very, you know, social, right?*

E: I would say for personal...umm... you know you really got a sense of community... in the LLC... for me *I was having a lot of friends there.*

In terms of building confidence, 93% of the student volunteers indicated an increase in their self-esteem due to volunteering at the centre, with 87% stating their efforts made them feel important. A couple of student volunteers touched on the self-esteem benefit in the focus group study, with one highlighting how she became more confident with taking risks:

B: I think for me, *I feel uhhh I gained confidence after uhhh helping out there* and then I uhhh *gained confidence in public speaking* and uh also through some of the workshops we did in the past.

A: *Yes, totally agree* [with B].

F: For me... when I first started... I didn't have that much experience... I was a little intimidated [and] always worried that I making a mistake. [But the facilitator] always told me ... *'take a risk because the worst that could happen is [it] wouldn't happen, simple. So it would be like... at least we tried and now we know.*

Although the focus group study did not address personal problems and how volunteering might have helped mitigate those challenges, the survey did address this. Table 1 shows 56.67% of the respondents in the survey noted that volunteering at the centre also helped them forget about their personal problems – translating, perhaps, into some emotional release or relief for the volunteers.

5 Discussion and Recommendations

It is important for all students to feel included, supported, and welcome at university. International and NNES students, however, often have complex emotional needs (Andrade, 2006; Constantine et al., 2004; Sawir et al., 2008). The results of this research suggest that the simple act of volunteering on campus could help student volunteers meet many of their needs and feel a greater sense of connection and belonging. This aligns with some of the aspects that Tran (2020) identified as important regarding interpersonal connections, namely, opportunities to engage academically, mentally, and emotionally. Sawir et al.'s (2008) Australian international student study, for example, revealed social isolation or loneliness as a significant impediment for new international students, particularly in their first semester of study. With this research study revealing 93% of the student volunteers reportedly felt less lonely and all felt part of something bigger, perhaps universities could strongly urge international students and domestic students to volunteer regularly on campus in their first semester. This means the university would need to build capacity for such opportunities and ensure that such opportunities were meaningful, inclusive, and well-supported. The act of volunteering, according to this study's findings, can not only give students a sense of belonging on campus but also provide students with accessible and welcoming opportunities to socially connect with others. Moreover, the student volunteers' efforts will most likely result in a greater feeling of confidence in themselves and their abilities. The act of volunteering has been linked to improved psychological well-being (Piliavin & Siegl, 2007), and the results of this study suggest that student volunteers benefited in their emotional well-being. Feeling part of something bigger, building social relationships, and fostering self-esteem all feed into nurturing a student's emotional well-being, so volunteering on campus should be encouraged, particularly in the case of international students and NNES. While this study is based on volunteer student participants in a Language Learning Centre at one university, it may be applicable and relevant to administrators and faculty in other academic settings. The findings are also significant for international graduate students and those who work with them. For those who direct or coordinate Language Learning Centres or other academic support spaces, it also highlights an important and less-investigated aspect of student volunteers on campus, and notably that of the emotional needs of students. The emotional well-being of students is an aspect that university faculty and staff need to have at the forefront of consideration in order to support the needs of these students.

6 Conclusions

In this article, the authors have argued that the act of volunteering in a Language Learning Centre played a role in fostering the emotional well-being of students, in particular NNES, in that they felt more connected and part of a broader teaching and learning community overall. The findings that emerged shed light on the lived experiences of volunteer students, particularly NNES graduate student volunteers, and their complex needs in adapting to life and study in a new country. While the step of putting one's name forward to serve as a volunteer and move out of one's comfort zone is something that some may find challenging, it does have some clear emotional benefits for students. For institutions, providing support and opportunities for students is critical not only for new arrivals, but for all students throughout their study. Opportunities for student volunteers should not be created for the sake of simply providing opportunities; they should have genuine substance and meaning. The emotional well-being of students needs to be at the forefront of educators' minds, and creating fulfilling opportunities for students to engage on campus through volunteer activities is one approach that can help mitigate students' feeling of isolation and improve their emotional well-being. Although this research is limited in size and scope and more studies are encouraged to confirm these findings, they do suggest volunteering as a coping tool for students from around the world – an important finding. Understanding how international students' volunteering in various capacities on campus could benefit them needs further investigation.

Findings will help administrators, faculty, and staff not only develop opportunities for both domestic and international students but do so in a way that takes into consideration the emotional well-being needs of student volunteers.

Appendix A: Survey Questions

1. I give my permission for my survey answers to be used as part of this research.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

2. How many semesters have you volunteered in the Language Learning Centre?
 - a. One
 - b. Two
 - c. Three or more

3. Is English your first language?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

4. What is your gender?

5. Which best describes your status when you have volunteered in the Language Learning Centre?
 - a. Undergraduate Student
 - b. Post-baccalaureate program student (e.g., TESL program)
 - c. Graduate student (e.g., Masters of Education)

6. On average, how many hours did you volunteer per week each semester?
 - a. 1-2 hours per week
 - b. 3-4 hours per week
 - c. 5 or more hours per week

7. Prior to volunteering in the Language Learning Centre have you worked as a volunteer in another capacity?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

8. If yes (you have been a volunteer previously), how did that experience influence your interest in serving as a volunteer in the Language Learning Centre?

9. Considering your personal and professional motivation and your experience as a volunteer, please indicate how important each of the following aspects is for you as a volunteer based on the following scale: 1. Strongly disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Agree, 4. Strongly Agree.

- a. Volunteering helps my professional development and growth
 - b. Volunteering is an opportunity to be part of a teaching and learning community
 - c. Volunteering provides me with the opportunity to explore different career paths
 - d. Volunteering is an opportunity to gain confidence as an educator
 - e. Volunteering will help me gain experience which will help in future job searches
 - f. I learn through helping others as a volunteer
 - g. I feel more connected to peers and others through volunteering
 - h. I have skills that can help other
10. Please consider the following statements and rate these based on the following scale: 1. Strongly disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Agree, 4. Strongly Agree.
- a. I am genuinely concerned about the students I support
 - b. I feel less lonely due to volunteering
 - c. Through volunteering, my self-esteem has increased
 - d. Volunteering makes me feel important
 - e. My friends volunteer and I want to work with them
 - f. Volunteering helps me learn about career options
 - g. I place a high value on community service
 - h. Volunteering helps me forget about some of my personal problems
 - i. I can learn how to work with a variety of people through volunteering
 - j. Volunteering is an opportunity to make new friends
 - k. My resume will be stronger with this volunteer experience
11. Do you feel that your work as a volunteer tutor made an impact? Please explain.
12. Are there any suggestions you have which you feel would improve your experience as a volunteer?

Appendix B: Focus Group Questions (Semi-structured)

1. When did you first volunteer in the LLC?
2. What was your main reason for volunteering?
3. Were there any secondary reasons?
4. How has your work at the LLC helped your future or your growth?
5. What was your favourite activity in the LLC?
6. In what ways can the facilitator of the LLC help you with your growth?

7. What else can we do to improve the LLC? more resources? physical space? more hours?
8. Any other comments?

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